

Pair Teaching in Computer Graphics

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Abstract

Computer Graphics is a course commonly found on Computer Science and Computer Engineering undergraduate programs. There are some convenient points on teaching computer graphics in these programs: Computer-Generated Imagery in movies and videogames are relevant examples of applied engineering and science that students experience in their lives, and this can be a potential motivation factor for students to get engaged on learning; furthermore, Computer Graphics relies on several fundamental and complex mathematical concepts, that can also be applied in other science areas, being an opportune moment to cover and practice mathematical learning goals, all connected with a base on computer science. Learning Computer Graphics depends on developing and integrating skills on computer science and mathematics, therefore, a learning plan must cover both topics. However, it must be considered that students need to relate these topics, and this is the trick, since ideally professors need the knowledge and pedagogy in both areas. The strategy presented in this document was based on two professors, one mathematician and one computer engineering, planning, and teaching an elective undergraduate course on Computer Graphics. The course was based on active learning strategies by design, heavily focused on Project Based Learning through three projects starting from scratch, each week learning and implementing new features on the projects. Students must program in regular programming languages like Python, C++ and Javascript, and build up their competence in mathematics from basic math concepts. As a result, students were able to develop a scanline renderer, and a ray-tracing renderer without any graphical Application Programming Interface and finally a 3D web application based on ThreeJS. Although students had a perception of a demanding course, they were engaged on proposed activities during all semester, and were able to implement all important features on projects, often above expectation, showing evidence that learning objectives were achieved.

Keywords: Pair Teaching; Computer Graphics Teaching; Mathematics Teaching; Project Based Learning.

1 Introduction

The foundations of Computer Graphics rely heavily on mathematical knowledge. Therefore, the proposal of a Computer Graphics course that is not limited to the mere application of ready-made programming codes requires a plan on how Mathematics will be incorporated into classes. This plan becomes even more important when considering Computer Graphics as an elective course at the end of an engineering program, as mathematics is too much concentrated in the beginning of the program, usually in the first semesters. This is a scenario in which students show less readiness for the application of mathematical concepts in the context of the discipline. As a result, many students may have difficulties with basic mathematical content, such as vector operations.

However, the development of a didactic sequence that resumes the mathematical knowledge required by Computer Graphics may represent a great challenge. As a computer engineer or a computer scientist, this professor may not master the content and/or pedagogy of the mathematical area. Furthermore, a clear understanding of the mathematics track in the undergraduate program, will allow course professors to identify topics of mathematics that were covered in previous semesters of the course, having a better view on what should be reviewed and what could be an entirely new topic for students.

In order to deal with this problem a pair teaching strategy (Andersson & Lars, 2006; Ott & Meek, 2019; Burden, Heldal & Adawi, 2012; Zehetmeier, Bottcher & Brüggemann, 2018) was adopted: two professors of different areas working together throughout the course. It is important to point out that this is not a course split in two parts having professors teaching their topics, professors have discussed and defined learning goals, planned classes and activities, and evaluated projects all together. At first this strategy may appear less efficient since there are two professors at the same time in class, but improvement on learning was very evident.

This paper reports the experience of pair teaching in a Computer Graphics course offered as an elective in an Engineering program. The course, based on an earlier version lectured by only a Computer Engineering professor, was taught by two professors: a computer engineer; and a mathematician. The remainder of the paper explains: the main pedagogical strategies in chapter 2, selected results achieved on conducted course in chapter 3, and final conclusions on chapter 4.

2 Strategy

Working in pairs for teaching can bring several benefits, but a clear alignment must be established between lecturers to create coherent activities in classes. The starting point for achieving this alignment was the plan and material produced in the previous version of the course, to ensure that developing computer graphics skills and course goals were maintained and improved as possible. Then, the mathematical content required for each course phase was identified. The organisation of mathematical knowledge was defined at the beginning of the program, to define the most appropriate depth, order, and approach during the course. Another important constraint is that courses should follow an active learning pedagogy heavily based on project-based learning.

Since this course is taught at the end of the engineering program, bringing back fundamental mathematical concepts could be very challenging. In this case, the profile of students enrolled in the course was necessary to better design activities in the mathematical area. Usually, students are more interested in working on more advanced projects, and very often they rely on tools or applications that hide the complexity of development, in this case on mathematics and computer science, but since the beginning students were informed that this course would dig in the fundamentals of mathematics and low level programming.

Thus, weekly demands were defined in the projects, most of which involving some type of mathematical knowledge and applied computer science. During classes, students worked in pairs or trios, guided by handouts that addressed the content required in that week's delivery. In this way, the progress concretely observed in their projects was the main motivation for studying the mathematics involved.

An example of this strategy was the study of rotations by quaternions. The representation of a three-dimensional object rotation by quaternions is a technique commonly used in computer graphics, since it avoids known problems of Euler's angles (Pletinckx, 1989). Its mathematical justification is based on the understanding of quaternions as a 4-dimensional space that contains complex numbers. More than just applying formulas to implement quaternion rotations in their projects, the proposed activities allowed students to have a real understanding of what they were doing in their programming code.

In addition to the weekly deliveries related to the projects, revisions were scheduled at strategic points in the course, which supported students to understand the big picture related to the procedures previously studied. These revisions were usually associated with the development of a complex case where students could check their understanding.

Three main projects were distributed during the semester that were further subdivided. The partial project deliveries have generally lasted a week, so that students could build their project and see some progress little by little.

2.1 Scanline Renderer

The first project was a conventional scanline renderer (Foley, van Dam, Feiner & Hughes, 1990). Students would initially implement an algorithm to identify 2D triangles and generate an image, but soon afterwards they would work in 3D, calculating the perspective view of a scene, calculating the lighting and traditional rendering resources such as anti-aliasing. Students had to develop from scratch using Python as a programming language. A skeleton code was provided by a git repository for them to follow the development and render some known sample scenes. The scanline render was designed to read X3D files (<http://www.web3d.org/>), what is a convenient format since it is open, well documented, and in text format, and all geometry can be parametrized.

The expected deliverables were:

- Render 2D colourful points, lines, and triangles
- Calculate perspective projection
- Render 3D triangles and triangle strips
- Rendering using super sampling
- Scene graph implementation
- Interpolate colours across triangles
- Texture map triangles
- Z-Buffer implementation
- Calculate illumination over triangles
- Render an animated scene

The deliverables were sometimes subdivided, and students were requested to implement and test their code with the examples. Balancing the level of complexity for the week's task was not simple since previous experience did not take into account the extra care with mathematical teaching.

2.2 Ray Tracer

The second project was a ray tracing renderer, for which Peter Shirley (2020) books were used as a basis. Initially students should implement the basics of the algorithm, following the book. The suggested language for this renderer was C++. In the sequence, challenges were proposed for the implemented ray tracing algorithms that students should fulfil. Ray tracing algorithms have a different strategy from scanline algorithms, but some mathematical concepts are reused, and some entirely new mathematical concepts were brought on this project.

One of the biggest differences from the first project, was the fact that ray tracing algorithms expect implicit representation of geometries, for instance, a sphere centred in the origin is represented by: $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = r^2$. This creates several new challenges for students that must adapt their mindset for this new project proposal.

The main deliverables were:

- Implement a new implicit geometry (like cylinders, torus, among others)
- Develop a texture based on some noise function
- Texture map a 3D object

The time for students to implement the basics of the renderer were 4 classes (classes are two hours long), although the algorithm documentation was very complete, students should take care of small details in order to compile the code successfully.

2.3 3D Web Project

The third and final project was the development of a theme free 3D application for web browsers. Students should implement a 3D scene using the ThreeJS 3D web API (<https://threejs.org/>) which is convenient as it does not depend on any specific platform, like Windows or MacOS. At that moment students were very creative, with curious scenes created.

Students were free to choose direction, but they must discuss with professors next steps, defining an adequate level of complexity for each intermediary delivery. This project management strategy was based on agile methodologies (Fowler & Highsmith, 2001), where professors would act as Product Owners.

3 Results

The results presented are based on the comparison to the previous version of the Computer Graphics course. The last version, in which pair teaching was adopted, allowed a greater advance both in programming and in mathematical learning evidenced by the quality of project deliverables. In the previous version, students did not progress as fast as expected because they had to review the mathematical concept by themselves without

proper support. For example, there was no time to discuss rotations with quaternions in the first version, as students were struggling with vector operations in describing rotations. And despite the denser content in the last version, students were able to fulfil most of the expected learning goals and tasks.

Another important point is how difficult it was for students in the previous version to connect what they did learn in math and how to use it on a real computer graphics application. Apparently, this connection was more natural for students that took the course with pair teaching.

These courses (last and previous versions) were taught at Insper (Soares, Achurra, & Orfali, 2016), and the educational institution collects blind feedback from students. Both courses were well evaluated by the students. Just, in the last version of the course, students pointed out that the course was more demanding than a regular elective, but this did not affect their motivation, and learning was enhanced due new activities planned.

There were some complaints about specific maths assignments charged at the beginning of the semester. Based on feedback, these deliverables have been discontinued, and content has been incorporated in project deliverables.

For the first part of the course, they were challenged to acquire all the expertise to develop a scanline rendering. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show some results from student's projects.

Figure 1. 2D render of points(a), lines(b) and triangles(c).

Figure 2. 3D render of triangle strips (a), texture maps (b) and scene graph (c).

Although the requested project was the same for all students, it is possible to see small details different from project submission to submission. One noticeable difference between each project submission was the time necessary to render 3D scenes. Rendering time was not a point for assessment, but some students did work on improving the performance of their algorithm, and at the end some complex scenes took a few seconds to render in some projects and in other projects took some minutes. This was also important for students to understand that rendering is a complicated process, and depending on the way you implement, algorithm run time and space requirements can exponentially grow as the input size grows (Chivers & Sleightholme, 2015).

The second project was based on a well-documented ray tracer (Shirley, 2020). Students had to implement the traditional ray tracer and after implement some kind of improvement for the system. Some of the implementation's results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Ray tracing render of cylinder (a), torus (b), drop (c) and spiral (d).

Shirley's book (Shirley, 2020) implementation shows only how to render a sphere, this is a convenient geometry for learning, but students were challenged with other geometries. In the end this was a complex task for students since it is possible to see some problems in most of the delivered results. We were expecting a cylinder in Figure 3 (a), although it is possible to recognize it, the calculation for surface normal is not correct, if normal were correctly calculated it would be possible to identify the interior part. Figure 3 (b), shows a torus that has a very complex equation to solve; students did an excellent job, but it is possible to visually confirm that normals were not well calculated. Figure 3 (c), shows a 3D drop, and again normal were not perfect and there is a small detail failing some render lines at the top of the drop. Finally, in Figure 3 (d) there is a spiral, the most complex geometry, students were able to correctly calculate normals, but they have to adapt the spiral equation.

As a second part of the second project, students were challenged on developing different textures, using noise functions, in particular Perlin Noise (Perlin, 1985), to create different materials. Figure 4 shows some results implemented by the students.

Figure 4. Materials created for a ray tracer using Perlin noise function among other techniques.

Students were very creative in creating new textures exploring mathematical functions. Professor's perception was that students enjoyed developing this creative work.

At the end, students had a complete free 3D project. This was an opportunity for students to create a more complex project and publish on the web for anyone to see. Students learned how to use a scene graph, in an advanced API (Application Programming Interface), in the case ThreeJS. Figure 5 shows some results from student's projects.

Figure 5. Sample images of theme free computer graphics web project.

There were several deliverables for the students during the semester, and students were a little concerned about the complexity of the topics in the course, and one student decided to leave the course. The first deliverables had an extremely high quality, and students were giving their best to accomplish the proposed challenges as best as they could. During the entire course topics had about the same level of complexity, but students start to burnout, and the deliverables were not so complete as used to be in the first part of the course. As professors start to notice that students were not delivering project with the same quality, they decided to slow down a little. In a future version of the course, professors should better balance how difficult are the projects and better track if students are burning out.

3.1 Difference between course versions

The most noticeable difficulty some students had in previous course versions was in vector operations. The course was not advancing as expected since skills in geometry transformations were necessary for the course and these are based on vector operations. In previous versions of the course this problem was tackled in a corrective way, as students started to struggle with vector operation, support classes were created. In the last course version, with two professors, vector and other mathematical topics were treated in a preventive way, but instead of a pure revision, students were oriented on how to learn the topic, with general exercises, readings, videos and even lectures to support students for their projects.

At the end, students could deliver projects with more details and quality, for instance in previous versions, the fourth part of the first project was not even published for students, since some support classes were necessary, and the original plan was delayed. On the second project in previous versions, only basic resources of the ray tracer were developed and in the last version not only the basic resources were implemented as some complex routines were also incorporated.

4 Conclusion

Having two professors on this computer graphics course, one mathematician and one computer engineer, allowed students to better discuss and learn several details in mathematics and computer science that otherwise would not be so practical. Classes were planned in an active way where students could discuss with professors graphical and mathematical techniques, also having studio time (that is time slots for developing their project in class) allocated for regular activities and project development.

There was a clear improvement on projects quality comparing the pair teaching version with previous version of the course with a single professor. In the pair teaching edition, students were able to implement more graphical techniques, and the quality is also noticeable. In the first edition, small mistakes on algorithms and math routines lead to imagens with some strange artifacts, what was not often noticeable in the pair teaching version.

The course has yet a lot of opportunities for improvement: for instance, in the first project a better sequence of topics can be used, in the second project the high dependency of an external book is not creating enough

opportunities for learning, and additional motivation for the final project can lead to better projects, what by consequence should improve learning.

5 References

- Andersson, R. & Lars, B. (2006). Pair Teaching – an eXtreme Teaching Practice. *In Pedagogiska Inspirationskonferensen*. issn: 2003-3761
- Burden, H., Heldal, R. & Adawi, T. (2012). Pair Lecturing to Enhance Reflective Practice and Teacher Development, in *Proceedings of Conference on Teaching and Learning*.
- Chivers, I. & Sleightholme, J. (2015). An Introduction to Algorithms and the Big O Notation. In: *Introduction to Programming with Fortran*. Springer, Cham. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-17701-4_23
- Foley, J. D., van Dam, A., Feiner, S. & Hughes, J. (1990). *Computer Graphics: Principles and Practice*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley. ISBN: 978-0-201-12110-0
- Fowler, M., & Highsmith, J. (2001). The agile manifesto. *Software development*, 9(8), 28-35.
- Ott, C. & Meek, N. (2019). Pair Teaching in Action. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-First Australasian Computing Education Conference (ACE '19)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 87–95. doi: 10.1145/3286960.3286971
- Perlin, K. (1985). An Image Synthesizer. *SIGGRAPH Computer Graphics 19* (0097-8930): 287-296. doi:10.1145/325165.325247
- Pletinckx, D. (1989). Quaternion calculus as a basic tool in computer graphics. *The Visual Computer 5*, 2–13 doi: 10.1007/BF01901476
- Shirley, P. (2020). Ray Tracing in One Weekend. url: <https://raytracing.github.io/>
- Soares, L. P., Achurra, P. & Orfali, F. (2016). A hands-on approach for an integrated engineering education. *Proceedings of the PAEE/ALE 2016*, p. 294-302.
- Zehetmeier, D., Bottcher, A. & Brüggemann, A. (2018). Designing Lectures as a Team and Teaching in Pairs. In proceedings of the *Fourth International Conference on Higher Education Advances*. doi: 10.4995/HEAD18.2018.8103.